

Structuring the WR Soepratman Street Corridor in the Context of Locality

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ABSTRACT

The road corridor of WR Soepratman Street in Bengkulu City is located within the education, trade and service sectors. These sectors have cultures that contrast with each other. These cultural differences are certainly not favorable in terms of functionality. People in the education sector really need the trade and service sector to support educational contributions. Meanwhile, trade and services need the education sector to improve the economy. Education cannot be separated from culture, even the quality of education is a measure of a nation's culture. Trade and services are actually fulfilled by educated people. Based on the research, there is an intersection of the two sectors in a commercial and cultural frame, without changing the functions that have been formed by maximizing the combination of the two sector functions and blurring the existing gaps.

INTRODUCTION

The road corridor of Jalan WR Soepratman Bengkulu City is a road corridor that is located between the education sector area, namely Bengkulu University, Primary School 69 Bengkulu City, MI Muhammadiyah with the trade and service sector. Both sectors have contrasting images of each other. The difference in image is certainly not favorable in terms of functionality. People in the education sector need the trade and service sector to survive, and both areas live day and night because of the trade and service sector, while the trade and service sector needs the education sector to support its market. Based on this, it does not demand the possibility of combining the images of the two sectors in one frame so that the relationship between the two sectors is better and mutually beneficial.

The growth of urban areas leads to an increase in activities that require space. However, the availability of space is limited to the area and dimensions of the city, which creates a need for public access to additional space (Mahendra.I.M.A, 2021). The presence of the education sector, specifically Bengkulu University, Primary School 69 Bengkulu City, and MI Muhammadiyah, has impacted the function of the surrounding land. Initially intended for housing, the area is now being utilized for trade and services, which presents economic potential in meeting the needs of the education sector. A research article by A. Munggiartia and I. Buchori (2015: 51-68) concludes that linking these two areas has negative impacts despite the benefits.

Based on this, it has triggered changes in the land use of the area, especially in the road corridor with a tendency to residential with a combination of service commercial activities. Some dwellings have been converted into stalls and boarding houses, and the emergence of the informal sector (street vendors) has also boosted the economy of the surrounding community. These changes have a direct impact on the condition of the road space that is the access to the campus (Fuji A and Sakura YI, 2018).

Urban dynamics can impact the urban fabric, particularly road corridors (Hendi, R.H.W.Abdulhadi et al, 2022). Mugi (2013) states that road corridors are essential for human activities and must be considered in urban design. This is supported by Hendi, R.H.W.Abdulhadi et al (2022). The WR Soepratman road corridor in Bengkulu City is lined with buildings that serve various purposes, including education, shopping, business, services, and residential purposes.

Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2021 regarding the Bengkulu City Spatial Plan 2021-2041 states that City Service Sub-Center V in Muara Bangkahulu District will function as a government, trade, and service center, as well as a hub for public service facilities, education, and security defense. The WR Soepratman road corridor is located in the Muara Bangkahulu District, which is an area for education, trade, and services. The development of a city can have a significant impact on various areas, particularly in education, trade, and services. This can lead to rapid development, which can shape the visual identity and character of a city. According to Lestari, Sari, and Rukayah (2021), visual quality is a crucial attribute of the visual system that is determined by both meaning and physical proportions in the environment.

Therefore, education and culture are intertwined, and the quality of education can serve as a measure of a nation's cultural development. Meanwhile, trade and services are carried out by educated individuals. It is possible for both sectors to intersect within a cultural framework. Without changing the function that has been formed by maximizing the combination of both land functions and blurring the existing image gap.

Figure 1. Concept diagram of the area

Thus, with the education sector located around the WR Soepratman Road corridor area, changes in the form of mass change in the WR Soepratman Road corridor will be different due to adjustments in trade and services provided. Thus, changing the form of the mass change requires processing the composition of various forms on the site in the realization of a physical design, which is carried out based on an approach by expressing certain functions, spaces and images.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Visual character

Krier (1988) argues that the visual character of building architecture is reflected in its elements, such as: a. The building facade comprises various elements, such as roofs, walls, arcades, doors, and windows. b. The building's interior space includes interiors, doors, windows, floors, columns, and ceilings. c. Building mass. The WR Soepratman Road Corridor utilizes three visual elements to create the building's architecture and alter its mass.

The assessment of visual quality in an urban landscape is based on the physical quality resulting from the relationship between visual elements. Hartono and Hamid (2019) identify at least seven criteria for evaluating visual quality in an area: a) Diversity refers to a range of different elements with varying patterns and arrangements. b) The term 'dominant' refers to a situation where one part is more prominent or influential than the other. c) Harmony is the combination of all the different parts into a unified whole. d) Intactness refers to the continuity of view and freedom from obstructions. e) Sequences are units organized according to specific patterns. f) Uniqueness: is a source, character or visual quality that is not commonly found on a regional or national scale; g) Unity: refers to a harmonious or appropriate composition between

landscape elements. In addition, the massing of the urban design is determined by the form and the relationship between the buildings in the form of distance, height, form and facade. This indirectly creates a space with a limit to the height or a skyline (Shirvani, H. 1985:11).

According to Kevin Lynch (1969), there are three components that significantly impact individuals' mental or visual representations of an area: (1) Identity: The city has the potential to be easily understood by its inhabitants and visitors through its urban image, which includes the identification of objects, differences between objects, and other recognizable characteristics. (2) Structure; Cities have the potential to be 'structured' which means that people can perceive urban space (object-object relationships, object-subject relationships, discernible patterns). (3) Meaning; The city has the potential to be experienced by people, meaning that they can perceive the urban space through two components: identity and urban structure. This understanding of meaning is based on dimensions such as symbolic, functional, emotional, historical, cultural, political, and spatial arrangement.

According to Fauzi and B. Sudawanto (2021) Visual is done, namely to provide direction for the character of the area as an orientation and marker of a city that is in accordance with the character of the area itself. The facade as a reflection of the interior layout, in a design, the facade is the most important thing that must be considered, because a building is always appreciated by the public by looking at the facade of a building.

Building form and mass

According to Shirvani, H. (1985:11) the shape and mass of buildings are the basic ingredients of architectural forms. Composing the form in the sense of organizing these single forms / elements into a total (final) form. The shape and order of the building masses concerns aspects of the physical form of the buildings, the aim is to achieve a balanced, proportional, harmonious, human-scale mass form by producing a mass order that forms outer space for outdoor activities (open space, pedestrian), by paying attention to the contextual surrounding buildings. Building codes are matters relating to the physical form that occurs as a result of a specific setting, which includes building height, setback, area closure (coverage), style, building volume density, scale, material, texture and style.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative method by taking a deductive approach with This research uses a qualitative method by taking a deductive approach by giving meaning to the visual character of the concept of mass composition resulting from variable components based on the theory used which becomes the benchmark in the process of obtaining data and analyzing based on the parameters of the theory used, namely the theory (Kevin Lynch., 1969) There are 3 components that greatly affect the mental image or image of people towards an area, namely identity, structure and meaning, and using the theory of Shirvani, H. 1985: 11. The observation location is on the WR Soepratman road

corridor starting from the Bengkulu University Rear Entrance Gate to SD N 69 which is an education area and trade and service area.

figure 2. The location of the observation

figure 3. The location of the observation

The research stages consisted of: (a) issues or phenomena that occur in the form of the influence of buildings on the WR Soepratman road corridor area. (b) The literature used as a basis is several theories to strengthen the topic and analysis of research on the form of building mass changes in which there is a visual character in building architecture based on the culture of Bengkulu Province. (c) Observation is carried out to be able to understand the topics of the problems raised based on the theory used. The implementation of this observation is in the form of a field survey or direct observation (d) Data processing is a follow-up to observation in the form of field surveys in the form

of photo documentation to be processed into 2 (two) dimensions using a computer. (e) Analysis in the form of design results that have been processed based on surveys, and theoretical studies used. So that the results of this analysis are in the form of building mass design images using (Kevin Lynch., 1969) and 3 (three) components that greatly affect the mental image or image of people towards an area, are identity, structure and meaning.

RESEARCH RESULT

The composition of the mass of urban planning is determined by the shape and relationship between buildings in the form of distance, height, shape and facade. This indirectly forms a space with a height limit or skyline, (Shirvani, H. 1985: 11). Building form and mass are closely related to building height, Density of building volume , Coverage, Setback, style, scale, materials, texture and color.

The concept of mass change on the WR Soepratman road corridor is formulated based on the theme that will be developed and described into ideas. This formulation process can be based on socio-cultural characteristics, activities, habits and spatial functions. So that the change of period in the building in the WR Soepratman road corridor, can have a characteristic that shows it as an education, service and cultural area of Bengkulu City, as a form of cultural heritage preservation is one type of approach in urban planning or spatial planning which aims to maintain, protect, maintain and utilize cultural heritage buildings for the benefit of development (Faghrezi.M.R, Satiawan.P.R, 2022).

a) Building Heights

The height of the building is related to the visibility of observers, both those inside the building and those on the pedestrian path. The height of buildings in an area forms a skyline. The WR Soepratman road corridor is dominated by one-story buildings, there are only a few two to three-story buildings in the form of shophouses.

Figure 4. The existing condition of building height is dominated by single-storey buildings.

b) Density of building volume

The WR Soepratman Street corridor is filled with diverse periods with different setbacks and distances between buildings that give the impression of difference and look light. As a commercial corridor, there is little potential

for building density, due to the variety of building forms and height restrictions, but this does not preclude the possibility of several buildings being joined together.

Figure 5. The existing condition of the building's sparseness looks light because of the differences in distance between buildings and differences in setbacks.

c) Setback

Setbacks on the WR.Supratman Road Corridor vary between buildings, ranging from 1.5 meters to 9 meters. Narrow setbacks make it difficult for vehicle users and pedestrians themselves due to the lack of space for movement and parking and often cause temporary congestion.

Figure 6. Existing conditions of building setbacks range from 1.5 meters to 9 meters.

d) Area closure (Coverage)

Ground closures on the WR Soepratman Road corridor appear to crowd the side of the road, leaving little open space between the road and the building but plenty of space at the back of the building. . With little green space between the building and the road, the Urban Heat Island effect is more pronounced due to the dominance of asphalt and concrete materials.

Figure 7. The existing condition of the area cover, it can be seen that development pattern focuses on the street side and leaves little space between the street and the building, and a lot of space at the back of the building.

e) *Langgam (Style)*

This street corridor is dominated by diagonal and horizontal shapes characterized by traditional to modern styles. The form of the piece is homogeneous but the style varies.

Figure 8. Existing condition of building style, there are traditional to modern styles

f) *Scale*

The scale of space that can be felt in this corridor is a wide terrace because the dominance of the height of the 1-storey building has minimal shade and on several sides it borders on campus-owned open space so that it has more interaction space between human vision and the sky and has a distant impression (Monumental Scale). The scale of the space is very large because the average height of the building is 1 floor and on some sides it borders the open space owned by the campus, giving a less intimate or warm impression

Figure 9. The existing condition of the space scale feels large (monumental scale)

g) Material

The role of materials relates to the visual composition of the design. The composition is realized by the relationship between visual elements. Materials between buildings in this road corridor vary, ranging from bricks, concrete, bamboo wood and all of them are united by the dominant material in the form of zinc as a roof. The reflection effect on zinc is also one of the factors disrupting thermal comfort in this corridor.

Figure 10. Existing condition of the building material

h) Texture

Being in a transitional area, the pattern formed is divided into two patterns. First, the commercial area, a development pattern that emphasizes the edge (edge defining block) and leaves a closed void in the center (central closed system), then the pattern formed in the form of ground (space / void) as figurative. While the second, the education area, places development inside and leaves open space on the edge, forming a figurative block pattern.

Figure 11. Existing condition of the texture pattern

i) Color

The colors in the WR Soepratman road corridor are dominated by bright and bright colors that are good for commercial areas

Figure 12. The existing condition of the color of the area is dominated by bright colors bright colors

DISCUSSION

based on the results of the analysis of the field survey, and the theoretical studies used. then it can be seen as follows:

a) Building Heights

there are several buildings that have a height of up to 3 floors, then this area has the potential to later develop and be filled with buildings with 2 to 3 floors, by maximizing the height of the building allowed can help meet the needs of user space.

Figure 13. Building height, can be increased up to the maximum permitted height

b) Density of building volume

Space optimization needs to be accompanied by a slight difference in facades between buildings in order to alleviate the impression of density when the building has been elevated.

Figure 14. Building height, can be increased up to the maximum permitted height

c) Setback

The distance of the building from the center point of the road is very important, for the arrangement of buildings. to regulate the order of buildings on the edge of the road. in addition, the distance between the building and the road will be a space that functions as a safety for road users or as pedestrian users. Therefore, it is necessary to expand the setback in accordance with the regulations planned by the region, which is half the road space plus 1 meter.

Figure 15. current setback conditions, some buildings have small setbacks.

Figure 16. The proposed setback is in accordance with the applicable The setback can function as pedestrian space, green space and vehicle parking.

d) Area closure (Coverage)

Application of appropriate setbacks, then the land cover at the front of the building is reduced and can be used as a space for landscaping. of the building is reduced and can be used as green space green space.

Figure 17. Direction Recommended closure area

e) Langgam (*Style*)

To blend the educational and commercial images, it is necessary to create a Commercial-Cultural image. Style direction can be through cultural frames on building facades and roof formations that create an area skyline.

Figure 18. Regional style direction through traditional roof formation

Figure 19. Regional style direction through traditional roof formation

f) Scale

The need to maximize the potential of built-up height to give a closer and warmer impression (Intimate Scale).

Figure 20. By optimizing building height and setbacks as green space makes the scale feel more intimate (Intimate Scale)

g) Material

The use of materials in buildings in the WR Soepratman road corridor area needs to maintain material diversity and slowly replace unifying materials with natural materials that are better or environmentally friendly. in order to support the planning direction of the cultured commercial area.

Figure 21. Direction of building materials and colors with the theme culture

h) Texture

Commercial areas and educational areas form ground (space or void) and figure (block) patterns, so that both patterns, the texture of the area formed is heterogeneous.

Figure 22. Existing condition of the texture pattern

i) Color

To support the formation of a cultural image, it is necessary to direct the color split between the buildings in the form of bright coloring on the lower floors that indicate commercial space and adjust the image branding between businesses and darker colors on the upper side to provide a cultural image.

Figure 23. Direction of building materials and colors with cultural themes

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The design of the area consists of several elements that must support and complement each other to create an area. Similarly, this element of the concept (maximizing space in the shop) will work if other design elements can be interconnected to reduce the impact of problems on the site. Utilization of the boundary line for parking and pedestrianization along the roadside. This will only be a normal change in general if it is not accompanied by other concepts such as pedestrian, circulation and parking, signage, land use, activity support, and other elements. The conclusions of the recommended form and mass recommended are as follows:

Figure 24. Existing dominated by one-story buildings with little distance between street space and buildings

Figure 25. *Setback & Area closure (Coverage)* the building period is set back, adjusted to local regulations. the space between the building and the road functions as parking and green space with minimal land cover.

Figure 26. height of the building the building period in the area has a height of 2 to 3 floors over time.

Figure 27. Style traditional style in the form of typical regional roof games as a form of commercial and cultural area formation, as a form of locality

Figure 28. Illustration of Design Implementation in perspective

Figure 29. Illustration of Design Implementation in front view

ADVANCED RESEARCH

The sustainability of this research is expected to emphasize the arrangement of pedestrian paths with inclusive design on the WR Soepratman

road corridor as a form of providing space for pedestrians and supporting the education area, as a form of sustainable design.

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REFERENCES

- A.Munggiarti, & I.Buchori, "Pengaruh keberadaan Perguruan Tinggi Terhadap perubahan Morfologi Kawasan Sekitarnya," *Geoplanning: Journal of Geomatics and Planning*, Vol.2, No.1, pp.51-68, April 2015. <https://doi.org/10.14710/geoplanning.2.1.51-68>
- Faghrezi.M.R,Satiawan.P.R. "Arahan Pengembangan Koridor basuki Rahmat Kawasan Kayutangan Kota Malang Sebagai Heritage Tourism," *Jurnal Teknik ITS*, Vol.11, No.3, pp. 160-166. 2022. [10.12962/j23373539.v11i3.96865](https://doi.org/10.12962/j23373539.v11i3.96865)
- Fauzi & B.Sudarwanto."Pengaruh fasade bangunan Terhadap Karakter Visual Kawasan Tugumuda Semarang." *Jurnal Arsitektur "ARCADE"* Vol.5, No.2, pp. 128-134. Juli 2021. <http://jurnal.universitaskebangsaan.ac.id/index.php/arcade/index>
- Fuji.A & S.Y.Iriani, "Karakter Spasial Koridor Jalan Kawasan Kampus dalam Konteks Urban Design Dan Perilaku." *Jurnal Arsitektur dan Perkotaan "KORIDOR"* Vol.09, no.01, pp. 121-135. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.32734/koridor.v9i1.1322>
- Hartono.D & Hamid A.H,"Identifikasi Elemen Fisik Ruang Publik yang Berpengaruh terhadap Pembentukan Visual Kawasan Kota Tua Jakarta,"*Emara: Indonesian Journal Of Architecture*, Vol.5 No.2, pp.75-79. Desember 2019. DOI: [10.29080/eija.v5i2.879](https://doi.org/10.29080/eija.v5i2.879)
- Hendi.A,R.W.Abdulhadi,T.M.Raja,A.R.N.Jannaty,A.W.Aura, "Identifikasi Transformasi Koridor Jalan IR. H Djuanda (DAGO) Bandung Sebagai Pembentuk Presepsi Pengguna," *Jurnal Arsitektur "ARCADE"* Vol.6, No.1, pp. 44-49. 2022. <http://jurnal.universitaskebangsaan.ac.id/index.php/arcade/index>
- Krier, R. (1988) *Komposisi Arsitektur* Jakarta: Jambatan.
- Lestari.K.B,Sari.R.S,Rukayah.R.S," Karakter Visual Gang Gambiran Kawasan Pecinan, Semarang," *Jurnal Arsitektur "ARCADE"* Vol.5, No.1, pp. 20-24. Maret 2021. <http://jurnal.universitaskebangsaan.ac.id/index.php/arcade/index>
- Lynch, K. (1960). *The Image of The City*. England: The M.I.T. Press
- Mahendra.I.M.A, " Identitas Kawasan Perkotaan Dalam Prespektif Atmosfer Kota (Studi kasus Kawasan Perkotaan Klungkung, Bali, Indonesia)," *Sustainable, Planing and Culture (SPACE): Jurnal Perencanaan wilayah dan kota*, Vol.3, No.1, pp 1-9. Juni 2021. <https://doi.org/10.32795/space.v3i1.1718>
- Peraturan Daerah No.4 Tahun 2021 Tentang Rencana Tata Ruang Wilayah Kota Bengkulu 2021 sampai 2041. <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Details/188182/perda-kota-bengkulu-no-4-tahun-2021>
- Proyek Inventarisasi dan Dokumentasi Kebudayaan Daerah. 1982. "Arsitektur Tradisional Daerah Bengkulu". Dekdikbud Provinsi Bengkulu. https://openlibrary.org/books/OL2519007M/Arsitektur_tradisional_daerah_Bengku lu.
- Shirvani, H. (1985). *The urban design process*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold. <https://archive.org/details/urbandesignproce0000shir/page/216/mode/2up>
- Smardon, R. C., & Palmer, J. F. (1986). *Foundations for visual project analysis*. Retrieved from https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_for_visual_project_analysis.html?hl=id&id=IvJOAAAAMAA
- T.Mugi. Penataan Koridor Jalan Jendral Sudirman Perkotaan Toboali, Kabupaten Bangka Selatan Dilihat Dari Elemen Rancang Kota (Desertasi). Universitas Teknik Universitas Pasuruan. 2013. <http://repository.unpas.ac.id/28999/>